

A Comprehensive Study of hassles in Aadhar Authentication and Biometric Security

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Abstract: The Indian Department of Information Technology introduced the idea of a universal electronic ID as part of an endeavour to give distinctive identification for each citizen across the nation. The goal of Aadhaar Authentication is to offer a digital, online identification platform so that the identity of people with Aadhaar numbers may be instantaneously verified whenever and wherever they choose. Individual information must be kept secure because Aadhaar numbers are linked to bank accounts, shares, mutual funds, and even mobile phones. Individual protection and information security are incorporated into the design of the UID project. The UIDAI act prevents the collection of sensitive personal data such as religion, caste, community, class, ethnicity, income, and health. Individual profiling is thus not possible using the UID system because the data collected is constrained to that required for identification and identity clarification. This paper focuses on UIDAI authentication and its security measures and the challenges faced.

Keywords

Aadhaar Authentication, UIDAI, biometric devices, CIDR, AUA, ASA

INTRODUCTION

India's national digital identity programme, Aadhaar, is the largest identity project in the world and aims to give every citizen a basic ID and access to government benefits. Aadhaar is linked to a variety of private sector services as well as national and state social programmes. Residents of India can use their 12-digit Aadhaar number to verify their identity and gain access to government social programmes. The Chief Economist at the World Bank, Paul Romer, called Aadhaar "the most advanced ID programme in the world".^[1]

To produce unique identities for all Indian citizens, the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) was founded. According to UIDAI, two concepts guided the design of this identity:

1. robustness to eliminate duplicate and fraudulent identities, and
2. verifiable [confirming identity data on ID formation] and authenticable [confirming identity

each time it is used] in an easy, cost-effective method.

PROCESS OF AADHAR REGISTRATION

Governmental registrars or non-governmental organizations working with UIDAI perform Aadhaar registration according to a tiered system. Automatic Biometric Identification Systems (ABIS) are provided to enrolment centres by three private sector companies. During the enrolment process, a combination of demographic information (such as name, gender, and date of birth) and biometric information is required (10 fingerprints, iris scans, and a photograph). A phone number or email address might be voluntarily provided as additional information. The Central Identities Data Repository (CIDR) is the recipient of this data after it has been transferred using the Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) or encrypted hard drives delivered by authorised carriers. Data from each new enrollee is compared to data from all previous enrollees in the database by the CIDR. This procedure is known as de-duplication. If the enrollee clears this process, a 12-digit Aadhaar number is generated and posted to the individual.

AADHAR AUTHENTICATION

The Central Identities Data Repository (CIDR), which verifies the information based on the available information, receives an Aadhaar number together with demographic or biometric data via the Aadhaar Authentication procedure. You must be verified to get state or federal assistance. To deliver consumer services, subsidies, or advantages, some service providers demand that clients produce identity credentials. While gathering these identity proofs, these service providers have trouble confirming or validating the accuracy of the documents or proofs supplied by individuals as to their identities.

The purpose of Aadhaar Authentication is to offer a digital, online identity platform where the identities of people with Aadhaar numbers can be promptly and remotely verified. This service is provided by UIDAI to confirm the identification of its clients or

workers before providing them access to their services or benefits.

MODES OF AUTHENTICATION

The following kinds of authentication are available: Demographic authentication, in which the Aadhaar number and demographic data are compared to the demographic data in the CIDR.

One-time-pin-based authentication, in which a One Time Pin (OTP) with a finite period of validity is transmitted to a mobile number or email address, and that number or email address is compared to the OTP created by the Authority.

Biometric-based authentication, in which the CIDR's data is compared to the Aadhaar number and biometric data.

Multi-factor authentication: This type of authentication may combine two or more of the aforementioned mechanisms.

According to its needs for strengthening security, a requesting organization may select the appropriate mode(s) of authentication from those available for a certain service or business function. For all forms of authentication, the Aadhaar number is mandatory. Only OTP and/or biometric authentication shall be used for e-KYC authentication. ^{[2],[19]}

BIOMETRIC AUTHENTICATION

The most often employed technique is biometric authentication. The data packet is encrypted by the authenticating system before being sent to the CIDR via the server of the authenticating service agency. The CIDR checks the received data package against its pre-stored parameters and responds with a yes or no (confirmation) decision.

Biometrics-based identification offers a mechanism to target interventions at a more specialized level in addition to informing the general public. Globally, there is a demand for more precise identification systems due to rising migration, security problems, and worries about electoral fraud, as well as what is perceived to be growing government scheme waste. Exclusion from a variety of rights and services, including health care, education, social welfare, and financial services, can result from a lack of legal identification. ^[3]

Security concerns ^{[4]- [9]}

In today's digital culture, identity theft is a growing concern. There have been numerous instances where private Aadhaar identifying information and demographic data have been exposed. Additionally, there have been cases where information leaks and hacking were possible with bank accounts connected to Aadhaar accounts. The UIDAI has put in place several safeguards to stop this from happening. It includes

the encryption of all data gathered at enrolment agencies and the restriction of decryption to the CIDR.

The UIDAI database only contains the bare minimum of data provided at the time of enrolment or update. source: author

After being decrypted, all biometric information is kept offline.

4. To ensure security, only the following people are allowed access to the database: Owners of Aadhaar numbers are the only people who have access to their personal data in the UID database. It will be protected with the greatest encryption and kept in a highly secure data vault, making it inaccessible to even many UID staff employees.

a) To restrict access to the database, CIDR operations will adhere to rigorous access protocols.

b) The database itself will be protected against threats like hacking.

5. Individual bank accounts, shares, mutual funds, financial and property information, health records, family, caste, religion, education, etc. are all things that UIDAI does not currently have and will never have in its database

6. Protocols for storage and security are in place. Any security infringement will result in serious fines, which also apply to identity information disclosure. Unauthorized access to CIDR can result in legal and criminal sanctions, including hacking charges and fines for altering CIDR data.

7. A small group of people with high clearance will physically and digitally guard the UID database. All-access information will be accurately logged.

8. All biometric authentication tools must be certified by the rules and standards set forth from time to time for this purpose by the Authority.

9. There is no transmission of unencrypted biometrics from the sensor to the host machine since every biometric record is processed and encrypted inside the safe zone.

10. Only the Aadhaar number, biometrics, and other information necessary for identity verification are sent to UIDAI by banks, mutual fund firms, mobile phone providers, etc. Such verification requests receive a "Yes" or "No" response from UIDAI.

11. Source data cannot be stored by ABIS vendors. They can only save enrollee data templates that are later sent for de-duplication. Use only UIDAI-approved authentication methods. An authentication service agency (ASA) or authentication user agency (AUA) must digitally sign the authentication using an encrypted channel (ASA).

12. Nobody can access a bank account and withdraw money with just their Aadhaar number. No other service, including banking, is available through it.

13. According to Regulation 17(1)(a) of the Aadhaar (Authentication) Regulations 2016, any asking entity, such as banks, mobile phone providers, and other businesses, is forbidden from keeping a copy of or distributing the fingerprints for any purpose. Any infringement of this clause will result in a punishable offence under the Aadhaar Act 2016.

14. The Punjab Artificial Intelligence System (PAIS), a face-recognition algorithm supported by artificial intelligence, is already being used by police officers in Punjab to apprehend criminals. By connecting it to Aadhaar data, they hope to significantly improve the precision and power of this AI.

15. The Crime and Criminal Tracking Network & Systems (CCTNS), a government-funded programme, is also building a biometric database of criminals across the country and plans to interface with the Aadhaar database to better detect criminals.

16. The Union Cabinet even wants to establish a national DNA database, which would violate citizens' rights even more and is very vulnerable to exploitation.

HASSLES OF AADHAR ^{[10]-[16]}

The most marginalized people in India are inconvenienced and left out by a variety of problems, including unreliable payment methods and subpar facilities. Emergency protections against "Aadhaar-related problems" in social programmes are urgently needed. Numerous such annoyances exist, frequently causing millions of people discomfort or worse, especially those from disadvantaged communities.

1. Excessive Aadhaar imposition: The Supreme Court judgment in September 2018 ruled that Aadhaar authentication can be made mandatory only for benefits paid from the Consolidated Fund of India and that alternative means of identity verification must always be provided when Aadhaar fails. Children were exempt.

Instead, Aadhaar continues to be routinely demanded from children for basic rights such as Anganwadi services or school enrolment. Similarly, for adults, alternatives to Aadhaar are often lacking, and even if there is one, people are kept in the dark about it – this has happened even for Covid-19 vaccination.

2. Arbitrary exclusions: According to a Supreme Court judgment in September 2018, alternate methods of identity verification must always be made available if Aadhaar fails and Aadhaar authentication can only be made mandatory for benefits received from the Consolidated Fund of India. Children weren't included.

Instead, Aadhaar is still frequently required of kids to access fundamental rights like Anganwadi services or school enrollment. Similar to children, adults frequently lack Aadhaar alternatives, and even if they have, they are kept uninformed about them. This has also happened with the Covid-19 immunization."

3. Inadequate facilities for Aadhaar enrolment, updating, and retrieval: Aadhaar enrolment,

updating personal information in the Aadhaar database, and recovering lost Aadhaar numbers have all become big difficulties for many even though they are now required. Many people, particularly the elderly or the crippled, were turned away from enrollment centres and don't know how to obtain an Aadhaar number. For those who are impoverished, updating their Aadhaar cards can be difficult, even for something as simple as changing their residence after getting married. Some people are urged to contact one of the UIDAI's eight regional centres, which would be an almost impossible undertaking for them to do.

4. Unreliable demographic details: Particularly the person's age, the demographic information on an Aadhaar card is frequently incorrect (date of birth). However, the age determined by an Aadhaar is frequently used to determine a person's eligibility for old-age pensions, school enrolment, or even to place a child in a specific grade. Furthermore, changing the age on an Aadhaar card can frequently be challenging without supporting documentation like a birth certificate.

5. Error-ridden Aadhaar Payment Bridge System: The demand to use the Aadhaar Payment Bridge System for direct benefit transfers, imposing ever-stricter and ever-changing Know Your Customer (KYC), or e-verification requirements, and linking bank accounts with Aadhaar has greatly complicated welfare payments. Welfare programmes have been troubled by payment issues in four different categories: delayed payments, rejected payments, redirected payments, and blocked payments.

6. Although biometric authentication offers instantaneous and paperless identification verification, its accuracy is not perfect. Up to 10 scans against the Aadhaar database may occasionally be required for a person to find a match. This takes a lot of time and is inaccurate.

7. To file and pay tax returns in India, it is now required by the Center that PAN (Permanent Account Number) accounts be linked with Aadhaar. Because South Indians use initials after or before their names, this poses a special challenge for that group. As a result, there may need to be a name change on either the PAN or Aadhaar card depending on the Aadhaar and PAN account discrepancy.

8. Any individual is unable to use certain services due to Aadhaar errors. Some of them might be necessary to him or her, rendering the proof of address or identity invalid. Correcting these mistakes will undoubtedly pull a person's attention away from their daily activities. Address mistakes and missing addresses are frequent mistakes, because they are challenging for authorities or agencies to detect.

Even those with privilege experience some of these inconveniences, but since they have special access to the solutions provided by online resources, interpersonal connections, and middlemen, they are comparably safe. Since they lack contacts, middlemen are frequently a source of additional exploitation for the poor. Despite being the primary sufferers of this situation, their struggles appear to be quite insignificant at the top.

SAFEGUARDS ^{[17],[18],[20]}

1. The Supreme Court issued several orders that the government must follow and carry out, including the limiting of mandatory Aadhaar to permissible reasons, the establishment of a backup plan if Aadhaar verification is unsuccessful, and the unconditional exemption of children.
2. Benefits should never be revoked or suspended without ex-post disclosure of all cases of deletion, with date and reason, and advance disclosure of the names that are likely to be deleted along with the proposed deletion, by issuing a show cause notice to those concerned and giving them a chance to respond or appeal.
3. The following amenities must be easily accessible to everyone, free of charge, at the block level or lower, in a well-managed public facility, according to UIDAI:
 - Aadhaar enrolment, such as enrolment of individuals with disabilities, missing fingers, missing irises, and others;
 - Updating Aadhaar biometric or demographic records without an appointment or long lines.
 - The retrieval of misplaced Aadhaar numbers under any circumstances.
4. Aadhaar cards shouldn't be used to verify an individual's age. For those without supporting documentation, updating their age in the Aadhaar database has to be made simpler.
5. An expert panel should conduct a thorough analysis of the Aadhaar Payment Bridge System and the direct benefit transfer systems.
6. The Reserve Bank of India and the National Payments Corporation of India should keep tabs on all varieties of payment issues and make thorough monthly reports available to the public.
7. The government should reconsider freezing further onboarding to the Aadhaar Payment Bridge System and halt pushing for a quick switch from "account-based payments" to "Aadhaar-based payments" under the direct benefit transfer system.
8. Rather than using the terminology of open source, the Indian government must release Aadhaar as actual open-source software and promote the use, growth, and adoption of open source as a foundation for the Aadhaar system.
9. It is important to keep track of the failures produced by OTP, biometric authentication, and other types of authentications because this data

might be beneficial. This may be with which authentication method encounters errors the most frequently, what has to be rectified, and which methods are most popular. If the public cannot access this information, no one will be held accountable.

CONCLUSION

An Aadhaar number holder's citizenship or place of residence is not established by their Aadhaar number or authentication on their own. It began as an innovative plan to lessen red tape and fraud. The UIDAI only uses the information it gathers to issue Aadhaar numbers and verify the identification of those who already have them. To establish uniqueness, the UIDAI is gathering biometric data, including a photo, 10 fingerprints, and an iris scan. There is no connection between the UID database and any other databases or the data included in them. Its sole function will be to confirm a person's identification while they are receiving a service and only with the owner of the Aadhaar number's permission. A small number of people with high clearance will physically and electronically guard the UID database. The data will be kept in a very safe data vault and protected with the greatest encryption. All-access information will be accurately recorded.

Thus, the Indian government has access to almost all of its residents' personal information. Through the use of their Aadhaar number, which will connect them to other services they use, they may monitor the activity of questionable individuals. The likelihood that the government would push for AI algorithms that automatically label some people as hazardous or suspicious is very high. These programmes would scan citizen behaviours and patterns. While this might aid in reducing crime and combating terrorism, it also runs the risk of making India a repressive surveillance state.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Anand, N. (2021). New principles for governing Aadhaar: Improving access and inclusion, privacy, security, and identity management. *Journal of Science Policy & Governance*, 18(01), 1-14
- [2]. <https://uidai.gov.in/aadhaar-eco-system/authentication-ecosystem.html> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [3]. <https://uidai.gov.in/ecosystem/authentication-devices-documents/biometric-devices.html> retrieved on 12/06/2022
- [4]. Pali, I., Krishania, L., Chadha, D., Kandari, A., Varshney, G., & Shukla, S. (2020). A Comprehensive Survey of Aadhaar and Security Issues. arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.09409.
- [5]. <https://uidai.gov.in/my-aadhaar/about-your-aadhaar/security-in-uidai-system.html> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [6]. https://uidai.gov.in/images/FrontPageUpdates/aadhaar_authentication_api_2_0.pdf retrieved on 10/06/2022
- [7]. <https://www.epw.in/engage/article/aadhaar-failures-food-services-welfare> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [8]. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/biometrics> retrieved on 09/06/2022

- [9]. <https://www.kaspersky.com/resource-center/definitions/biometrics> retrieved on 10/06/2022
- [10]. Zende, S. S. (2022). Digitalization In India Prospect And Challenges. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship & Technopreneur (INJETECH)*, 2, 29-37.
- [11]. Mohammed, A. S. Privacy And Security Risks With Aadhar Card: Study Of Media Discourses On Reporting Various Third-Party Data Breaches.
- [12]. Barde, S. (2018). A multimodal biometric system-aadhar card. *i-manager's Journal on Image Processing*, 5(2), 1.
- [13]. Madan, H. K. S. D. S. A Study On Aadhar Privacy And Personal Security Issues In India.
- [14]. <https://scroll.in/article/1013700/six-types-of-problems-aadhaar-is-causing-and-safeguards-needed-immediately> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [15]. <https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/campaigns/aadhaar/key-challenges-and-way-forward/> retrieved on 20/06/2022
- [16]. <https://jsis.washington.edu/news/the-aadhaar-card-cybersecurity-issues-with-indias-biometric-experiment/> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [17]. Banerjee, S. (2016). Aadhaar: Digital inclusion and public services in India. *World Development Report*, 81-92.
- [18]. Agrawal, S., Banerjee, S., & Sharma, S. (2017). Privacy and Security of Aadhaar A Computer Science Perspective.
- [19]. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aadhaar> retrieved on 09/06/2022
- [20]. https://uidai.gov.in/images/notification_dated_04_02_2022.pdf retrieved on 20/06/2022